

**KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT OF TEACHER EDUCATORS OF B.ED.
COLLEGES IN RELATION TO THEIR TOTAL QUALITY
MANAGEMENT**

Mrs Priti Suresh Chandorkar

Research Scholar

University Of Mumbai

Research Guide: Dr. Ratnaprabha Rajmane

Abstract

Knowledge Management has been explored and researched by scholars for more than twenty years and it continues to be an area of interest for scholars. Knowledge Management (KM) is a program or system designed to create, capture, share and influence knowledge towards the success of the organization. The paper aims to obtain greater understanding of the relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed. colleges. This paper shows that there is a significant positive relationship between Knowledge Management and Total quality Management. If knowledge Management increases, there is significant increase in the Total quality Management.

Key words: *Knowledge Management, Total Quality Management, Teacher Educators.*

Introduction:

With product life-cycles restriction and technologies becoming increasingly imitable, organization knowledge emerges as a major source of competitive advantage. Knowledge Management (KM) is a term that arose approximately two decades ago, roughly in 1990. Knowledge management is the systematic management of an organization's knowledge assets for creating value and meeting tactical & strategic requirements. It consists of the initiatives, processes, strategies, and systems that sustain and enhance the storage, assessment, sharing, refinement, and creation of knowledge and leverage knowledge towards the success of the organization. In simple words, knowledge

management incorporates both holding and storing of the knowledge perspective, with respect to the intellectual assets.

The concept of TQM was initially developed in Japan, and its origins can be traced in the work of the – so-called – quality gurus, Deming, Juran, Feigenbaum, TQM views an organization as a collection of processes. It maintains that organizations must strive to continuously improve these processes by incorporating the knowledge and experiences of workers. The simple objective of TQM is ‘Do the right things, right the first time, every time’. Knowledge management has great impact on Total Quality Management of the institution. Teacher Educators who develop the Knowledge management will be able to improve their total quality management of the institution.

Statement Of The Problem: “Knowledge Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed. colleges in relation to their Total Quality Management”

Review of Related Literature:

Knowledge Management

Researches Done In Abroad

Prayong Thitithananon (2015) explores an implementation of KM practices in Thailand’s Higher Education development by using ICT tools for improving the current education systems in order to be agreement with the royal decree of rules and regulations in excellence of country management.

Noa Aharony (2014) made an investigation on the use of Wiki in a Knowledge Management Academic Course to support discussion during the process of creating and sharing knowledge, for the delivery of class curriculum and projects and to enable students and instructors to be in a continuous discussion, which can be used as a knowledge repository. The research is focused on comprising wiki pages which were gathered from knowledge management wiki course in Israel and aims to explore and analyze the application and use of a wiki, a key concept of in a knowledge management academic course.

Frank Nyame-Asiamah (2013) has stated to examine the contributions and suitability of the available knowledge management (KM) technologies, including the Web 2.0 for exploiting tacit knowledge. It proposes an integrated framework for extracting tacit knowledge in organizations, which includes Web 2.0 technologies, KM tools, organizational learning (OL) and Community of Practice.

Researches Done In India

Saxena Anurag (2015) asserted the application of KM technologies in different areas like study material development data, student registration data, support services data, study material production and distribution data and evaluation and certification data for distance education courses in IGNOU.

Rathinavelu (2014) explored the importance of ICT to create and share high quality multimedia contents through web based knowledge sharing system by developing Kshare system for collaborative learning among teachers and students through intranet within the institution to acquire, utilize and share knowledge by using ICT.

Alok Sharma (2013) prepared a software tool EDULOGIC for engineering institutions for imparting quality education in a highly structured, controlled and quantified manner. The data, content and results produced over contiguous years build the necessary ground for managing the related accumulated knowledge for students and faculty.

Total Quality Management

Researches Done In Abroad

Yang (2015) found that TQM practices including quality management, process management, employee empowerment and teamwork, customer satisfaction management, quality goal setting and measurement, supplier's cooperation and quality tools training have positive effects on customer satisfaction and that the adoption of TQM principles is an effective means by which companies can gain competitive advantage.

Reed (2014) provided an excellent account of the theoretical underpinning of TQM.) TQM programs have become a key focus for many organizations, and are likely to remain a key issue for many companies in the new century.

Researches Done In India

Rajan (2014) studied diffusion of TQM concept in the Cheruvannur- Nallalam Grama Panchayat in Kozhikode district as a tool for attaining good governance. The Grama Panchayat proved how TQM could be adapted to a local government situation and implemented for effective public administration. Perhaps, this is the first Panchayat in Kerala or in India to apply TQM for improving the service delivery system.

Siddiqui and Rahman (2013) gives a detailed description of the introduction of TQM for the Information Systems (IS) in India. They evaluated the extent of their relationship in terms of awareness and utility. The study indicates the TQM awareness amongst IS professionals and TQM benefits for IS functions such as improved customer satisfaction,

enhanced quality of products and services delivered to the customer, and increased flexibility in meeting the customer demands.

Need of the study: The study of this type is very essential because it will suggest ways and means to involve employees in improving the quality enhancement of the organisation. The research is intended to throw light on the relationship between knowledge management and Total Quality Management. This will help the colleges to improve with the help of teacher educator's skill of knowledge management. Through this study, teachers-educators will become aware Knowledge Management and Total Quality management of their own organisation. It will also provide them the understanding of their own weakness and strength which will further help them to attain total quality management for their institution. So, researcher got eager to explore to know is there any relationship between Knowledge Management (KM) and Total Quality Management (TQM). Hence, there is a need to study of Knowledge Management of Teacher Educators in relation to their Total Quality Management.

Objectives of the study:

1. To ascertain the relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges on the basis of following variables.
 - Total Sample
 - Location of Institution.(Urban,rural)
 - Gender

Null Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges on the basis of following variables
 - Total Sample
 - Location of Institution.(Urban,rural)
 - Gender

Research Methodology: The present study has adopted the descriptive method of the correlational and causal comparative types for processing the data, classifying, analysing and interpreting the findings

Sample: Data is collected from 113 respondents. Simple random sampling method is used to collect data. Information is collected only from teacher educators affiliated to

Mumbai University.

Variable of the study are as follows:

- Knowledge Management
- Total Quality Management

Sub variables

- Location of Institution.(Urabn,rural)
- Gender

Data Analysis: In the process of testing of hypothesis Statistical tools Karl Pearson's correlation is applied.

Null Hypothesis H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed. colleges on the basis of

- Total Sample
- Location of Institution.(Urabn,rural)
- Gender

Hypothesis Testing:

Null Hypothesis H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges on the basis of

- Total Sample

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management			
Sub-variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Total Sample	0.341	0.020	Significant

Interpretation: The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management is 0.341. The respective calculated p-value is 0.020. It is less than 0.05. Therefore, the test is rejected. Hence Null hypothesis is rejected.

Finding is that there is a significant positive relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management. If Knowledge Management increases, there

is significant increase in the Total Quality Management on the basis of total sample.

Conclusion: There is significant relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges on the basis of total sample.

Null Hypothesis H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges on the basis of

- Location of Institution.(Urban,rural)

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management			
Sub-variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Location: Urban	0.091	0.439	Not significant
Location: Rural	0.430	0.024	significant

Interpretation: The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between the Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management for various Location category. For urban are Pearson's correlation value is 0.091 and corresponding p-value is 0.439. Since p-value is greater than 0.05. Test is accepted. Null hypothesis is accepted, for rural are Pearson's correlation value is 0.430 and corresponding p-value is 0.024. Since p-value is less than 0.05. Test is rejected. Null hypothesis is rejected.

Finding is that there is a significant Negative relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management for the urban respondents, while a Positive significant relationship for the rural respondents.

Conclusion: There is significant positive relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management for respondents from Institutes in Rural area. If Knowledge Management. Increases, there is significant increase in the Total Quality Management.

Null Hypothesis H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges on the basis of

- **Gender**

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its

significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management			
Sub-variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Gender: Male	0.371	0.035	Significant
Gender: Female	0.430	0.017	Significant

Interpretation: The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between the Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management for gender of respondents. All the respective calculated p-values are less than 0.05. Therefore, the test is rejected. Hence Null hypothesis is rejected.

Finding is that there is a significant Positive relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management for the female respondents, while a Negative relationship for the male respondents.

Conclusion: There is significant relationship between Knowledge Management and Total Quality Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to the gender of respondents.

Suggestions:

- Knowledge Management (KM) program bringing in relevant knowledge in the form of competitor benchmarking information. Best quality-improvement projects should be started as employee-ideas from structured idea-generation initiative, a part of the KM program.
- Strategic Knowledge management programme should be implemented. E.g. KM initiatives (such as knowledge bases, communities of experts and collaboration) centered on pre-defined “mission-critical” areas.
- Technology as an important enabler, but clearly one component of a larger KM program

Conclusion: The use of the best technology and organizational culture where people are ready to share their knowledge with others, proven the best total quality management of the organisation.

References

Best, J. W. and Kahn, J. V, (2003): Research in Education. (9thed). New Delhi:

<https://asq.org/blog/2015/09/how-does-knowledge-management>